

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

NEUROMARKETING AND SUSTAINABLE CONSUMER BEHAVIORS

Giljov R.

*Master's degree student at Vilnius University
Kaunas faculty of International Business management*

ABSTRACT

Advertising plays a crucial role in shaping consumer behavior, influencing their perceptions, attitudes, and purchase decisions. Sustainable marketing has emerged as a new promotional strategy, focusing on social and environmental resources. However, businesses have been slow in implementing neuroscience in sustainable product advertisement. Neuromarketing, which applies neuropsychology to market research, can be used as a cognitive engineering tool to promote sustainable behaviors. In this review paper, we examine the effects of advertising on consumer behavior and the potential of neuromarketing to promote sustainable behaviors. We conclude that sustainable advertisements should be created in a way that captures the attention of the audience, inspires them to want the product, and motivates them to act on it. Further research is needed to understand how neuromarketing can be used to shape and develop deeper awareness toward more sustainable consumption.

Keywords: advertising, consumer behavior, sustainable consumption, environmental awareness, neuromarketing, cognitive engineering, social media, branding, marketing communication, green products.

Introduction

Advertising is an essential component of marketing, aiming to influence consumer behavior by promoting products and services through various media channels. The power of advertising lies in its ability to shape consumer perceptions, attitudes, and purchase decisions. The relationship between advertising and consumer behavior has been studied extensively, with research focusing on the impact of advertising on brand awareness, brand loyalty, and purchase intentions/ [17, p.489-514] Consumer behavior is influenced by various factors, including social norms, personal values, cultural background, and individual experiences. Advertising has been found to affect consumer behavior by creating a sense of familiarity with the product and by influencing consumers' attitudes and beliefs about the product. [14, 55-84] Consumer familiarity with a product is essential for its market share, and businesses use print, digital, or a combination of these platforms to market their goods. The emergence of sustainable marketing has highlighted the need for businesses to focus on social and environmental resources. Sustainable marketing aims to promote more sustainable consumption patterns and solutions to socio-ecological issues through environmentally friendly products and accompanying advertising. Despite the potential of sustainable marketing, businesses have been slow in implementing neuroscience in sustainable product advertisement. Neuromarketing is a new technique that applies neuropsychology to market research, aiming to better understand individuals' sensorimotor, cognitive, and emotional reactions to marketing stimuli. It uses non-invasive techniques to measure brain activity, enabling researchers to examine subconscious motives that influence individual behaviors. [21, p.199-204] The potential of neuromarketing to promote sustainable behaviors has yet to be fully explored.

The relevance of the topic of advertising and consumer behavior, with a focus on sustainable consumption, is significant in today's world. With the growing

awareness of environmental issues, consumers are becoming more mindful of their choices and their impact on the environment. Companies and businesses are under pressure to reduce their carbon footprint and implement sustainable practices. One of the ways they can do this is by promoting sustainable products and encouraging sustainable consumption.

Advertising plays a crucial role in shaping consumer behavior and influencing their purchasing decisions. By using persuasive techniques and targeting specific demographics, advertisements can effectively increase awareness and demand for sustainable products. Neuromarketing, which applies neuropsychology to market research, can be used to better understand consumers' sensorimotor, cognitive, and emotional reactions to marketing stimuli. This technique can be used to improve advertising campaigns and create more effective messaging that appeals to consumers' emotions and values.

The topic is relevant not only to businesses and advertisers but also to policymakers and consumers. Governments are introducing policies to promote sustainable consumption, and consumers are increasingly looking for more eco-friendly products. By understanding the impact of advertising on consumer behavior, policymakers can make informed decisions on policies and regulations that promote sustainable consumption. Consumers can also use this knowledge to make more informed choices and reduce their environmental impact.

Research statement: Neuromarketing can be used to promote sustainable consumer behaviors by influencing consumer decision-making processes.

Neuromarketing and Consumer Behavior. Definition of neuromarketing

Neuromarketing is a field of study that uses insights from neuroscience to understand how consumers respond to marketing and advertising messages. It is an interdisciplinary field that combines psychology, neuroscience, and economics to investigate how the brain is physiologically affected by marketing stimuli. The

goal of neuromarketing is to evaluate the effectiveness of marketing strategies by measuring and monitoring brain activity resulting from exposure to advertising and marketing messages, using neuroimaging techniques such as fMRI and EEG. By understanding how consumers respond to marketing messages on a neurological level, marketers can gain insights into what drives consumer behavior and create more effective marketing campaigns. [21, p.199-204]

The role of neuromarketing in influencing consumer behavior

Studies by McClure revealed a correlation between neural activity and brand familiarity as well as product preference. [23, p.379-387] The role of neuromarketing in influencing consumer behavior, specifically in terms of brand familiarity and product preference. It shows how neuromarketing can help measure and understand the neural basis of consumer decision-making, which can then be used to inform marketing strategies and influence consumer behavior. According to the findings of a study that was carried out by McClure and colleagues [23, p.379-387], neuromarketing research is able to measure the efficiency of brand identification and emotional connection. According to the findings of the study that looked at the role of reward circuitry in the brain in connection to brand memory and emotional attachment, it was discovered that Coca-Cola fared significantly better than Pepsi did. Based on these findings, neuromarketing research appears to have the potential to play a substantial part in influencing the behavior of consumers.

Research employing functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) has provided evidence of the capacity to predict consumer choices and preferences (Walter, 2005). For instance, advertisements incorporating humor have been found to stimulate greater activity within the ventromedial prefrontal cortex, a brain region involved in processing reward value and risk during decision-making, which subsequently correlates with increased sales. Moreover, Walter et al. identified activation within the nucleus accumbens when participants were exposed to images of vehicles, particularly sports cars, and granted the opportunity to drive them, leading to positive emotional responses.

Techniques and tools used in neuromarketing research

The field of neuromarketing research uses a wide variety of methods and instruments to glean information about the preferences and behaviors of consumers. Eye-tracking, functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), and electroencephalography (EEG) are three of the methods that are utilized the majority of the time. In the field of neuromarketing research, the most common types of neuroscience-based technologies utilized are fMRI and EEG, among other neuroimaging methods. EEG measures brain activity in terms of electrical activity at the scalp using numerous electrodes placed on the participant's scalp in a net-like fashion, whereas fMRI measures neural activity throughout the brain in terms of blood flow via oxygen usage. fMRI measures neural activity throughout the brain in terms of blood flow via oxygen usage. Researchers are now

able to perform conditioning and marketing experiments, as well as monitor participants' responses utilizing both behavioral responses and brain activations, all thanks to these tools. According to Fugate [11], neuromarketing entails connecting participants to various electronic equipment and creating quick, vivid pictures of a working brain to examine variations in the visuals produced throughout the various tasks. Notwithstanding initial limitations in neuroimaging methods that impeded the spatial resolution and precision of the findings, the area of neuromarketing has advanced fast over the course of the last several years.

Sustainable Consumer Behaviors. Definition of sustainable consumer behaviors

The concept of sustainable consumer behaviors has gained significant attention in recent years, driven by the increasing awareness of the environmental, social, and economic consequences of human actions. Sustainable consumer behaviors represent a shift in consumption patterns and decision-making processes that prioritize the long-term well-being of both human societies and ecosystems. As the global population continues to grow and natural resources become scarcer, understanding and promoting sustainable consumer behaviors become imperative for addressing environmental degradation and fostering equitable development.

Defining sustainable consumer behaviors involves examining the choices and actions taken by individuals in the context of acquiring, using, and disposing of goods and services. These behaviors are informed by an understanding of the interdependence between human actions and the natural environment, and they encompass a wide range of practices aimed at reducing resource consumption, minimizing waste, and supporting ethical and responsible production methods.

Numerous academic disciplines contribute to the understanding of sustainable consumer behaviors, including sociology, psychology, marketing, environmental studies, and public policy. This interdisciplinary approach helps elucidate the underlying motivations, barriers, and potential pathways for fostering sustainable consumption. As the study of sustainable consumer behaviors continues to evolve, researchers and policymakers strive to develop effective strategies that encourage individuals to adopt environmentally and socially responsible consumption habits. This, in turn, supports global efforts to mitigate climate change, preserve biodiversity, and promote social justice for current and future generations.

Many scholars try to understand and define the suitable consumer behaviors such as Jackson. [16, p.30-40] Although Tim Jackson's report does not explicitly present a concise definition of sustainable consumer behaviors, it delves into an extensive examination of the elements shaping sustainable consumption and the ways it can be encouraged. By analyzing the report, we can deduce a general notion of Jackson's perspective on sustainable consumer behaviors.

Jackson characterizes sustainable consumption as the utilization of goods and services fulfilling fundamental needs while reducing the consumption of natural resources, toxic materials, and emissions of waste and pollutants.

In her work, Seyfang [29, p.63-82] does not explicitly define sustainable consumer behaviors but, she discusses the broader concept of sustainable consumption and the importance of grassroots innovations in promoting behavioral change towards more sustainable practices. Seyfang [29, p.63-82] explores the concept of sustainable consumption and the role of grassroots innovations and alternative economic models in promoting eco-friendly consumer practices and emphasizes the need to shift from a linear "take-make-waste" economy to a circular model focused on reducing resource use, reusing materials, and recycling waste. Sustainable consumer behaviors, as inferred from Seyfang's discussion, involve choosing low-impact goods and services, minimizing consumption and waste, supporting ethical and green products, fostering a sharing economy, and engaging in alternative economic systems that prioritize social and environmental goals over profit.

Scholars Schaefer and Crane [28, p.76-92] although not provide a specific definition of sustainable consumer behaviors. However, they discuss the broader concept of sustainable consumption and its implications for marketing and policy.

The authors emphasize the importance of understanding and addressing the relationship between consumption and sustainability. They argue that sustainable consumption involves rethinking consumer practices to minimize the negative impacts on the environment and society, and to promote long-term well-being.

Sustainable consumer behaviors can be defined as a constellation of actions and decision-making processes employed by individuals, aimed at minimizing their ecological footprint, conserving natural resources, and fostering social equity throughout the entire lifecycle of products and services. These behaviors encompass conscious choices that prioritize environmentally responsible practices, fair labor conditions, and the ethical treatment of animals, with the ultimate objective of ensuring the long-term well-being of both human societies and ecosystems.

In the context of this definition, the term "consumer" refers to individuals who purchase, use, and dispose of goods and services, thereby exerting direct or indirect effects on the environment and society. Sustainable consumer behaviors can manifest in various forms, including but not limited to, the adoption of eco-friendly products, reduction of resource consumption, avoidance of unnecessary waste, and support for businesses with established corporate social responsibility initiatives.

These behaviors are informed by an awareness of the interdependence between human actions and the natural environment, as well as an understanding of the need for long-term solutions that foster social, economic, and environmental sustainability. By engaging in sustainable consumer behaviors, individuals actively contribute to the preservation of the planet's resources, the mitigation of environmental degradation, and the promotion of social justice for current and future generations.

The importance of sustainable consumer behaviors

The significance of sustainable consumer behaviors has become increasingly paramount in light of global environmental challenges, the pursuit of equitable development, and the mounting pressures on finite resources. [6; 24, p.531-537] Such behaviors play a critical role in mitigating the adverse consequences of human consumption on the environment, addressing the mounting issues of resource scarcity, and fostering social equity and responsible production methods. [16, p.30-40; 29, p.63-82]

Embracing sustainable consumption practices allows individuals to contribute to the long-term welfare of human societies and ecosystems alike, supporting worldwide efforts to address climate change, preserve biodiversity, advance social justice, and transition towards a circular economy [28, p.76-92; 29, P.63-82] This transition implies shifting from the current linear "take-make-waste" model to a more sustainable model that emphasizes reducing resource consumption, reusing materials, and recycling waste, ultimately leading to more efficient resource management and reduced environmental impacts. [29, p.63-82]

Understanding the determinants of sustainable consumer behaviors, along with the obstacles impeding their adoption, is crucial for devising efficacious strategies that promote environmentally and socially responsible consumption patterns. [16, p.30-40] This perspective has ramifications for a range of academic disciplines, encompassing sociology, psychology, marketing, environmental studies, and public policy, which together contribute to the interdisciplinary examination of sustainable consumption. [6]

Furthermore, the importance of sustainable consumer behaviors extends to businesses and policymakers who must consider the growing consumer demand for environmentally responsible products and services. [28, p.76-92] By incorporating sustainability into their core values and practices, businesses can not only meet consumer expectations but also improve their competitiveness and long-term viability in the market. [24, p.531-537]

As scholars and policymakers persist in investigating the relevance of sustainable consumer behaviors, their findings will guide the development and execution of targeted interventions designed to cultivate sustainable lifestyles and consumption practices. [24, p.531-537] These interventions may include policy measures, educational campaigns, and infrastructure development that support and facilitate the adoption of sustainable behaviors among consumers. [16, p.30-40]

In summary, the importance of sustainable consumer behaviors is evident in their potential to alleviate environmental pressures, foster social equity, and facilitate the transition to a more sustainable and circular economy. By understanding the drivers and barriers of such behaviors and developing targeted interventions, scholars, businesses, and policymakers can work together to promote a future characterized by responsible consumption and equitable development.

Factors influencing sustainable consumer behaviors

Sustainable consumer behaviors are shaped by a complex interplay of individual, social, and contextual factors that influence people's decisions to adopt environmentally friendly practices and consumption patterns. Understanding these factors is essential for designing effective policies, marketing strategies, and educational initiatives to encourage sustainable lifestyles.

Individual factors, such as personal values, beliefs, environmental awareness, knowledge, and emotional factors, play a critical role in shaping sustainable consumption patterns. People's attitudes towards the environment, motivations, and perceptions of the impact of their actions on the environment determine their likelihood of engaging in sustainable behaviors. Social factors, including social norms, peer influence, social identity, and cultural values, significantly affect sustainable consumer behaviors. People often conform to the expectations and behaviors of their social circles, and their consumption patterns are influenced by the values and norms prevalent in their communities and cultures. Lastly, contextual factors, such as the availability and accessibility of sustainable products, pricing, convenience, incentives, regulations, marketing, and labeling, shape sustainable consumer behaviors. The physical and economic environment, as well as government policies and market forces, can either facilitate or hinder the adoption of sustainable consumption patterns.

Considering the complex interplay of individual, social, and contextual factors, researchers, policymakers, and practitioners can develop a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing sustainable consumer behaviors. This understanding can guide the development of targeted interventions and strategies to promote sustainable lifestyles and consumption patterns among diverse populations.

Auger, Devinney, and Louviere [2, p.299-326] study consumer ethical beliefs across countries using the best-worst scaling methodology, examining consumers' preferences and trade-offs regarding ethical product attributes such as environmental friendliness, labor conditions, animal welfare, and fair trade. While not directly discussing factors influencing sustainable consumer behaviors, their research provides insights into consumers' preferences and values, which can be linked to sustainable consumer behaviors.

The study highlights the importance of considering cultural differences and local contexts when examining sustainable consumer behaviors, as consumers across different countries showed varying preferences for ethical product attributes. Furthermore, the best-worst scaling methodology enables researchers to understand the relative importance of different ethical attributes in consumers' decision-making processes. This information can identify factors that may be more influential in promoting sustainable consumption and be used to develop effective marketing strategies and policies targeting specific ethical attributes valued by consumers.

Gifford [12, p.290] investigates the psychological barriers that impede individuals from participating in

climate change mitigation and adaptation efforts, which are pertinent to understanding the value-action gap in sustainable consumer behavior. This research complements Blake's [3, p.257-278] examination of the "value-action gap" in environmental policy, which underscores the disparity between individuals' pro-environmental attitudes and their actual behavior. While not directly addressing sustainable consumer behavior, both studies provide valuable insights into the barriers that prevent individuals from acting in line with their pro-environmental values. Gifford's [12, p.290] work on psychological barriers, along with Blake's [3, p.257-278] identification of four primary barriers—individuality, responsibility, practicality, and inertia—contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing sustainable consumer behaviors. Overcoming the value-action gap necessitates addressing individual, social, and contextual barriers that discourage people from translating their pro-environmental attitudes into action. Both studies highlight the importance of integrated approaches, which include policy measures, education, and infrastructural changes, to facilitate and encourage sustainable consumer behavior.

Bolderdijk, Gorsira, Keizer, and Steg [4] examine the role of individual values in determining the effectiveness of informational interventions aimed at promoting pro-environmental behavior. They focus on how aligning informational interventions with people's values can either enhance or undermine the effectiveness of such interventions in promoting sustainable consumer behaviors.

Drawing on the value-belief-norm theory, the authors distinguish between egoistic (self-oriented) and biospheric (nature-oriented) values. Their experiments demonstrate that the effectiveness of informational interventions depends on the congruence between the values promoted in the intervention and the participants' dominant values. Specifically, interventions emphasizing biospheric values were more effective in promoting pro-environmental behavior among participants with stronger biospheric values, while interventions targeting egoistic values were more effective among participants with dominant egoistic values.

The study by Bolderdijk et al. [4] underscores the importance of taking individual values into account when designing interventions to promote sustainable consumer behaviors. Their findings suggest that a "one-size-fits-all" approach to informational interventions may be less effective, as people with different dominant values may respond differently to the same intervention. Instead, tailoring interventions to align with the target audience's values can enhance the effectiveness of these interventions in promoting sustainable consumer behaviors.

In conclusion, understanding the complex interplay of individual, social, and contextual factors is crucial for promoting sustainable consumer behaviors. By examining studies that explore various aspects of these factors, such as personal values, cultural differences, barriers to pro-environmental action, and the effectiveness of tailored interventions, researchers, policymakers, and practitioners can develop targeted strategies to

encourage sustainable lifestyles and consumption patterns. This multifaceted approach is key to addressing the challenges of sustainability and fostering environmentally responsible behavior across diverse populations.

Neuromarketing and Sustainable Consumer Behaviors. How neuromarketing can be used to promote sustainable consumer behaviors

A relatively new branch of study called "neuromarketing" combines neuroscience and marketing to look at how customers react emotionally and cognitively to different stimuli. [11] Using neuromarketing insights to encourage sustainable consumer behaviors is essential as sustainability gains importance in today's global climate. By examining attention, emotions, and decision-making processes, this study intends to address the possible implications of neuromarketing in promoting sustainable consumer behaviors.

Focus and perception: Marketers may create sustainable products and campaigns that successfully attract and hold consumers' attention by using neuromarketing, which provides insights into how people allocate their attention. Individuals have a finite number of cognitive resources available to them for information processing, according to the Limited Capacity Model of Motivated Mediated Message Processing (LC4MP). [20, p.46-70] Neuromarketing research can discover visual components that draw attention and promote cognitive processing by using eye-tracking technology [35, p.123-147]. For instance, adding vibrant colors and eye-catching images to packaging or marketing for sustainable products may enhance customer attention and, as a result, sustainable consumption.

Emotions: Consumer behavior is greatly influenced by emotions. [15, p.132-14] Research on neuromarketing can be used to pinpoint the emotional cues that promote sustainable consumption. When customers come across sustainable products or ads, for instance, neuroimaging techniques like functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) can be used to assess the neurological correlates of emotions. [18, p.532-538] These results can then be used to develop emotionally engaging marketing messages that encourage sustainable consumption. [33, p.436-452] Also, addressing the psychological obstacles to sustainability, such as eco-guilt or eco-anxiety, might be crucial in encouraging ecologically friendly consumption. [13, p.209-220]

Methods for Making Decisions: The cognitive mechanisms that drive decision-making are better understood thanks to neuromarketing. Marketing professionals can create tactics that encourage sustainable decisions by understanding the neurological mechanics underlying customer decision-making. For instance, research have revealed that the activation of brain areas linked to reward and value-based decision-making affects customers' willingness to pay for sustainable items. [27] So, by emphasizing the personal benefits and rewards of sustainable purchasing, marketers can use this knowledge to create tactics that will make it more likely for customers to choose sustainable options.

In essence, by developing a greater knowledge of attention, emotions, and decision-making processes, neuromarketing presents tremendous opportunity to encourage sustainable consumer behaviors. Marketers can design persuasive ads that persuade people to engage in more environmentally and socially conscious consumption by utilizing these data. Overall, neuromarketing provides valuable tools and knowledge that can be harnessed to promote sustainable consumer behaviors, ultimately contributing to a more environmentally conscious and socially responsible society.

The effectiveness of neuromarketing in promoting sustainable consumer behaviors

Neuromarketing has emerged as a powerful tool for understanding consumer behavior, offering unique insights into cognitive and emotional processes that drive decision-making. [11] This paper discusses the effectiveness of neuromarketing in promoting sustainable consumer behaviors, examining the impact of various neuromarketing techniques on attention, emotions, and decision-making processes.

Attention and Perception: Neuromarketing techniques have proven effective in capturing and retaining consumer attention, which is crucial for promoting sustainable behaviors. [35, p.123-147] By utilizing eye-tracking technology, researchers can identify visual elements that stimulate cognitive processing and design sustainable products and campaigns that effectively engage consumers [35, p.123-147] Consequently, the ability to optimize marketing materials to capture attention increases the likelihood of consumers adopting sustainable consumption patterns. [20, p.46-70]

Emotions: Emotions play a significant role in influencing consumer behavior, and neuromarketing has demonstrated its effectiveness in evoking emotional responses that encourage sustainable consumption. [15, p.132-140] By employing neuroimaging techniques such as functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and electroencephalography (EEG), researchers can identify emotional triggers that drive sustainable behavior. [18, p.532-538] For example, the use of emotionally charged marketing communications can evoke positive feelings towards sustainable consumption and motivate consumers to adopt environmentally friendly practices. [33, p.436-452]

Decision-making Processes: Neuromarketing has proven effective in understanding the cognitive processes underlying consumer decision-making, enabling the development of strategies that promote sustainable choices. [27] By examining the neural mechanisms of reward and value-based decision-making, researchers can develop marketing strategies that emphasize the personal benefits and rewards of sustainable consumption, increasing the likelihood of consumers choosing sustainable options. [27] Additionally, neuromarketing insights can inform the design of choice architectures and nudges that subtly influence consumers towards more sustainable behaviors. [31]

In addition to the aforementioned factors, neuromarketing has demonstrated effectiveness in leveraging social influence to promote sustainable consumer behaviors. By incorporating social proof elements in mar-

keting campaigns, such as testimonials, ratings, and endorsements, marketers can tap into consumers' inherent desire for social approval and conformity, thereby driving sustainable choices. For example, the "I Will If You Will" campaign by Earth Hour and the World Wildlife Fund (WWF) successfully employed social influence to encourage participants to pledge sustainable actions.

Moreover, neuromarketing has proven effective in utilizing the power of personalization to promote sustainable consumption. By tailoring marketing messages and product offerings to individual preferences, marketers can increase consumer engagement and foster a sense of connection with the brand. In turn, this can lead to the adoption of sustainable consumer behaviors, as consumers are more likely to support brands that align with their personal values and beliefs. [22, p.18-31]

Furthermore, neuromarketing research has uncovered the effectiveness of using counterintuitive messaging to drive sustainable behavior. For instance, Patagonia's "Don't Buy This Jacket" campaign successfully leveraged counterintuitive messaging to engage consumers and convey the brand's commitment to sustainability. This approach effectively disrupted traditional marketing norms and resonated with consumers, ultimately contributing to the adoption of more sustainable consumption practices.

In conclusion, neuromarketing has demonstrated its effectiveness in promoting sustainable consumer behaviors by providing valuable insights into attention, emotions, decision-making processes, social influence, personalization, and counterintuitive messaging. By leveraging these insights, marketers can develop powerful strategies that encourage consumers to adopt more environmentally friendly and socially responsible consumption practices.

Ethical Considerations of Neuromarketing

The interdisciplinary subject of neuromarketing has drawn a lot of interest due to its potential to provide light on consumer behavior and decision-making processes. [11] However, the application of neuromarketing raises ethical concerns of deceit, privacy, and informed consent. [25, p.293-302]

Privacy and data protection: Participants' sensitive neurophysiological data, such as brain activity patterns and biometric responses, are commonly collected in neuromarketing studies. [10, p.230-237] Because it's possible for personal information or preferences to be made public using the data without the person's knowledge or consent, this raises privacy concerns. [1. P.284-292] To address these difficulties, researchers and practitioners must adhere to strict data protection laws, ensuring that data is collected, maintained, and processed while respecting the privacy of research participants [8, p.687-702]

Independent and Manipulative: Neuromarketing approaches, according to their detractors, could undermine consumer autonomy by enabling advertisers to sway consumers' decisions by using their unconscious brain functions. [32,p1271-1284] In response, proponents of neuromarketing contend that understanding consumer behavior has always been a marketing objec-

tive and that neuromarketing just provides a more accurate understanding of consumer preferences. [21, p.199-204] Nonetheless, it is imperative for neuromarketing experts to uphold ethical standards by ensuring that marketing strategies do not capitalize on consumer decision-making weaknesses or undermine personal autonomy.

Sensible Consent: Informed consent, which guarantees that participants are fully informed of the study's goals, methods, risks, and rewards, is a crucial feature of research ethics. It may be challenging for participants to understand the complicated procedures used in neuromarketing research, making it more difficult to gain informed consent. [25, p.293-302] Researchers need to make sure that participants have the opportunity to inquire about the study and withdraw without facing consequences in order to address this issue. Also, they must ensure that the goals and procedures of the study are briefly and clearly communicated. [8, p.687-702]

As neuromarketing matures, it is crucial to consider its ethical implications. By addressing privacy issues, doing away with manipulation, and ensuring informed permission, researchers and practitioners can uphold ethical standards and strike a balance between innovation and consumer protection.

Future Developments in Neuromarketing and Sustainable Consumer Behaviors

The discipline of neuromarketing, which blends marketing with neurology, has showed promise in terms of its ability to provide light on consumer behavior and decision-making, particularly in connection to sustainable consumption. [11] New avenues for study and application are opening up as technological development continues.

Technological developments in neuroimaging: As neuroimaging technologies continue to advance, such as functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), electroencephalography (EEG), and magnetoencephalography (MEG), they will provide us a better understanding of how the brain influences consumer behavior. [18, p.532-538] These developments will make it possible for academics to investigate the intricate relationships between social, emotional, and cognitive aspects that affect sustainable consumption, aiding in the creation of more focused and successful marketing campaigns. [33, p.436-452]

Combining machine learning and artificial intelligence: It has great potential to improve the analysis and interpretation of neurophysiological data if artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) are integrated into neuromarketing research. [5] Researchers can use AI and ML algorithms to find patterns and links in massive datasets, allowing them to gain a more detailed understanding of the elements that influence sustainable consumer behavior. [7] Also, these technologies can make it easier to create tailored marketing plans that take into account unique interests and beliefs, thus encouraging sustainable purchasing. [19, p.1710-1740]

Uses for Virtual and Augmented Reality: Technologies like augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) present brand-new potential for neuromarketing study and implementation. Researchers can examine

consumer behavior in ecologically valid settings by immersing customers in realistic and engaging virtual environments, increasing the external validity of neuromarketing findings. [30, p.3549-3557] Additionally, incorporating VR and AR into marketing efforts may offer creative ways to convey sustainability messaging and encourage customers to make sustainable purchasing decisions.

Inter-disciplinary Partnerships: More multidisciplinary cooperation in neuromarketing is projected to occur in the future, bringing together specialists from disciplines including psychology, economics, and environmental science to create a more thorough understanding of sustainable consumer behavior (Ariely & Berns, 2010). By taking into account variables including social norms, individual incentives, and structural impediments, this multidisciplinary approach will encourage the creation of more efficient and comprehensive ways to promote sustainable consumption. [22, p.18-31]

Future improvements in neuromarketing, such as those in neuroimaging technologies, AI and ML integration, VR and AR applications, and interdisciplinary collaborations, have a substantial impact on the promotion of sustainable consumer behaviors. Researchers and marketers may create creative and successful tactics to promote more environmentally and socially responsible consumption habits by utilizing these breakthroughs, ultimately helping to create a more sustainable society.

Conclusion

This review paper has explored the role of advertising in shaping consumer behavior, the growing importance of sustainable marketing, and the potential application of neuromarketing in promoting sustainable consumption. Advertising influences consumer perceptions, attitudes, and purchase decisions, and businesses can leverage this to promote environmentally friendly products. Neuromarketing, as a technique that applies neuropsychology to market research, provides deeper insights into consumer responses to marketing stimuli, which can be utilized to develop more effective sustainable advertising strategies. In conclusion, neuromarketing has the potential to promote sustainable consumer behaviors by influencing the decision-making processes of consumers and encouraging them to choose eco-friendly products and practices.

Future research should focus on understanding the specific aspects of neuromarketing that can be employed to shape and develop a deeper awareness of sustainable consumption. Further investigation is needed to identify the most effective cognitive, emotional, and sensorimotor triggers that promote environmentally responsible behaviors. Additionally, collaboration between businesses, policymakers, and researchers is essential to create comprehensive strategies that leverage neuromarketing techniques to encourage sustainable consumption. Ultimately, fostering sustainable consumer behavior will require a multi-faceted approach that combines advertising, public policy, and consumer education initiatives to address the complex social and environmental challenges that we face.

References

1. Ariely, D., & Berns, G. S. Neuromarketing: the hope and hype of neuroimaging in business. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 11(4), 2010, p. 284-292.
2. Auger, P., Devinney, T. M., & Louviere, J. J. Using best-worst scaling methodology to investigate consumer ethical beliefs across countries. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 70(3), 2008, 299-326.
3. Blake, J. Overcoming the 'value-action gap' in environmental policy: Tensions between national policy and local experience. *Local Environment*, 4(3), 1999, p.257-278.
4. Bolderdijk, J. W., Gorsira, M., Keizer, K., & Steg, L. Values determine the (in)effectiveness of informational interventions in promoting pro-environmental behavior. *PLoS one*, 8(12), 2013, e83911.
5. Calvo, R. A., D'Mello, S., Gratch, J. M., & Kappas, A. (Eds.). *The Oxford handbook of affective computing*. Oxford Library of Psychology, 2015.
6. Cohen, M. J., Brown, H. S., & Vergragt, P. (Eds.). *Innovations in sustainable consumption: New economics, socio-technical transitions and social practices*. Edward Elgar Publishing, 2013.
7. Davenport, T. H., & Harris, J. G. *Competing on analytics: The new science of winning*. Harvard Business Press, 2007.
8. Dimoka, A., Pavlou, P. A., & Davis, F. D. Research commentary—neuroIS: the potential of cognitive neuroscience for information systems research. *Information Systems Research*, 22(4), 2012, p.687-702.
9. Does In-Store Marketing Work? Effects of the Number and Position of Shelf Facings on Brand Attention and Evaluation at the Point of Purchase. *Journal of Marketing*, 73(6), p.1-17.
10. Fisher, C. E., Chin, L., & Klitzman, R. Defining neuromarketing: practices and professional challenges. *Harvard Review of Psychiatry*, 18(4), 2010, p. 230-237.
11. Fugate, D. L. Neuromarketing: a layman's look at neuroscience and its potential application to marketing practice. *Journal of consumer marketing*, 2007.
12. Gifford, R. The dragons of inaction: psychological barriers that limit climate change mitigation and adaptation. *American psychologist*, 66(4), 2011, p. 290.
13. Grob, A. A structural model of environmental attitudes and behaviour. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 15(3), 1995, p.209-220.
14. Hameed, I., Khan, M. B., & Shahab, A. Perceived humor and purchase intention: mediating role of attitude towards the advertisement and brand. *The Lahore Journal of Business*, 8(2), 2020, p. 55-84.
15. Holbrook, M. B., & Hirschman, E. C. The experiential aspects of consumption: Consumer fantasies, feelings, and fun. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 9(2), 1982, p.132-140.
16. Jackson, T. Motivating sustainable consumption. *Sustainable Development Research Network*, 29(1), 2005, p.30-40.
17. Kasser, T. Materialistic values and goals. *Annual review of psychology*, 67, 2016, p.489-514.
18. Kenning, P., & Plassmann, H. How neuroscience can inform consumer research. *IEEE Transactions*

- on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering, 16(6), 2008, p.532-538.
19. Ladeira, W. J., Nardi, V. A. M., Santini, F. D. O., & Jardim, W. C. Factors influencing visual attention: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 35(17-18), 2019, p.1710-1740.
20. Lang, A. The limited capacity model of mediated message processing. *Journal of Communication*, 50(1), 2000, p.46-70.
21. Lee, N., Broderick, A. J., & Chamberlain, L. What is 'neuromarketing'? A discussion and agenda for future research. *International journal of psychophysiology*, 63(2), 2007, p.199-204.
22. Luchs, M., Naylor, R. W., Irwin, J. R., & Raghunathan, R. The sustainability liability: Potential negative effects of ethicality on product preference. *Journal of Marketing*, 74(5), 2010, p.18-31.
23. McClure, S. M., Li, J., Tomlin, D., Cypert, K. S., Montague, L. M., & Montague, P. R. Neural correlates of behavioral preference for culturally familiar drinks. *Neuron*, 44(2), 2004, p.379-387.
24. Mont, O., & Plepys, A. Sustainable consumption progress: should we be proud or alarmed?. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 16(4), 2008, p.531-537.
25. Murphy, E. R., Illes, J., & Reiner, P. B. Neuroethics of neuromarketing. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, 7(4-5), 2008, p.293-302.
26. P. A., Vo, K., Hampton, W., Bollinger, B., ... & Winer, R. S. Predicting advertising success beyond traditional measures: New insights from neurophysiological methods and market response modeling. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 52(4), 2015, p. 436-452.
27. Plassmann, H., O'Doherty, J., & Rangel, A. Orbitofrontal cortex encodes willingness to pay in everyday economic transactions. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 27(37), 2007, p. 9984-9988.
28. Schaefer, A., & Crane, A. Addressing sustainability and consumption. *Journal of macromarketing*, 25(1), 2005, p.76-92.
29. Seyfang, G., & Seyfang, G. Grassroots Innovations for Sustainable Consumption. *The New Economics of Sustainable Consumption: Seeds of Change*, 2009, p.63-82.
30. Slater, M. Place illusion and plausibility can lead to realistic behaviour in immersive virtual environments. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 364(1535), 2009, p.3549-3557.
31. Thaler, R. H., & Sunstein, C. R. *Nudge: Improving decisions about health, wealth, and happiness*. Yale University Press. 2008.
32. Ulman, Y. İ., Cengiz, E., & Şener, E. M. Ethical issues in neuromarketing: "I consume, therefore I am!". *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 21(5), 2015, p.1271-1284.
33. Venkatraman, V., Dimoka, A., Pavlou, P. A., Vo, K., Hampton, W., Bollinger, B., ... & Winer, R. S. Predicting advertising success beyond traditional measures: New insights from neurophysiological methods and market response modeling. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 52(4), 2015, p. 436-452.
34. Walter, H., Abler, B., Ciaramidaro, A., & Erk, S. Motivating forces of human actions: Neuroimaging reward and social interaction. *Brain research bulletin*, 67(5), 2005, p.368-381.
35. Wedel, M., & Pieters, R. A review of eye-tracking research in marketing. *Review of Marketing Research*, 4, 2008, p.123-147.